

SPECIFIC ASPECTS IN THE APPLICATION OF BLOOM'S TAXONOMY IN LABORATORY EXERCISES

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Abstract. *In this article, methods of using Bloom's taxonomy, which form students' skills such as knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation, during the course of laboratory training on physics, are presented. Examples of all levels of Bloom's taxonomy in the process of teaching physics are given. The laboratory work "Determining Planck's constant using the photo effect phenomenon" intended for academic lyceums was analyzed based on this taxonomy.*

Keywords: *taxonomy, Bloom's taxonomy, knowledge, understanding, analysis, application, synthesis, evaluation, photo effect.*

INTRODUCTION.

In today's innovative environment, modernizing processes aimed at increasing the efficiency of the current lesson, providing education and training to students, is considered as an approach that guarantees knowledge transfer and mastery. Taking into account the importance of being able to apply the acquired knowledge in practice, the tasks of improving the teaching methodology and introducing innovative projects into this process increase the responsibility of teachers-pedagogues.

The worldview, way of thinking and interests of the growing young generation certainly create a need for national and global educational trends [1]. Therefore, such a need in the educational process is based on case-based problem-based teaching tested in national experiences, the "Socratic approach" based on questions and answers, constructivism (John Dewey), which is successfully used worldwide, and the development of the child's intellect (Jean Piaget), diversity of intelligence (Howard Gardner), the area of closest development (Lev Vygotsky), person-oriented education (Dorothy Dow Nolt) requires the rational use of theories and approaches. These theories help students to communicate freely, to achieve variety of opinions in discussions, and to create a healthy competitive environment in the group.

Professor Benjamin Blum of the University of Chicago and a number of educational scientists created a taxonomy that develops and evaluates the characteristics of a person in cognitive and individual-emotional fields as a result of their research. The term "taxonomy" comes from a Greek word that means systematization. This term was introduced to science in 1813 by the Swedish botanist O. Decandol. In our opinion, taxonomy is the classification of objects and principles in the field of education based on their compatibility with each other.

Creating an environment where students enjoy learning is one of the most important elements of being an effective teacher. We can use all kinds of strategies and lesson plans, but none of them will matter if our students don't understand the information we're teaching. Developing the skills necessary to learn from Bloom's Taxonomy is key to creating an effective classroom environment in which our students can benefit from our instruction [2].

In practice, Bloom's taxonomy shows that the cognitive, affective (emotional) and psychomotor (motor) spheres of educational goals manifest themselves during the activities of

teachers and pedagogues, requires a rational choice of methods of imparting knowledge to students, as well as ensuring student activity in the group and clearly planning the stages of the lesson.

In the "Cognitive" field of education, students develop the skills to remember the acquired knowledge, learn new information and apply it in practice.

In the affective field, students develop their interest and inclination to study subjects, and their emotional and personal relationships with other students in the group are decided. The creative abilities of the test taker are evaluated [3].

In the psychomotor field, it is envisaged to form students' manual labor, creative products, and practical skills. More specifically, these concepts mean things like "I know," "I feel," and "I create."

The application of Bloom's taxonomy to the cognitive field includes 6 educational goals. They are:

1. Knowing—remembering and consolidating information based on clear evidence. At this level, the student remembers rules and values based on short, concrete facts.

Examples of levels of knowledge:

- the student knows the value of the acceleration of free fall.
- the student tells the law of straight motion.
- the student tells the value of Avagadro's number at the end of the lesson

2. Comprehension - represents goals such as understanding the exact essence of the information, rules, drawings or tables learned during the lesson, being able to transfer the educational material from one type to another, imagining and interpreting the processes that will take place on the basis of these.

Examples of level of understanding:

- The student can explain the phenomenon of dispersion.
- Can calculate the direction and value of the field strength.
- Can find the velocity of an object in uniform motion.

3. Application - it is related to the student's ability to correctly and appropriately use the knowledge learned not only in the subject itself, but also in unfamiliar situations. This level

requires the student to introduce, define, use, implement and apply tasks and forms the competence to apply theoretical knowledge in practice.

Examples of application levels:

- Using Coulomb's law, the student can calculate the electric field strength of a point charge.

- Students can apply the heat balance equation for fluids at different temperatures.

- Can create thermonuclear reactions.

4. Analysis is the level of first dividing it into parts, and then determining their characteristics and the relationship between them, in order to understand the studied information in a general state.

Examples of level of analysis:

- At the end of the lesson, students will be able to analyze what forces act on a body moving on an inclined plane.

- Can apply the 1st law of thermodynamics to processes.

- Students can analyze the amount of heat in different parts of parallel and series connected circuits.

5. At the Synthesis level, students explore different elements and ideas and combine them to create new ideas or structures. They learn to identify and draw conclusions from common themes and patterns

- Can determine the internal energy of an ideal gas from the isochoric process graph.

- Can determine the properties of new elements formed in thermonuclear reactions.

- Can apply Newton's laws in other inertial reference systems.

6. Evaluation. At this level, which is considered the last stage of Bloom's taxonomy, students evaluate the events based on all the reasons they have learned during the whole lesson, and think about the issue. As a result, their logical and philosophical thinking develops.

Examples of grade level:

- Can estimate the amount of heat released in thermal processes.

- Can compare the useful work coefficients of real and ideal heat engines according to the Carnot cycle.

- Can calculate the ratio of the scattering angles of the spectra to the propagation speed in the case of dispersion.

As can be seen from the examples mentioned above, all physical processes in nature correspond to a certain stage of Bloom's taxonomy.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Many works on the application of Bloom's taxonomy to the educational process attract our attention. In particular, our researchers K.Amonov and A. Baratov [4] conducted a number of works on the formation of physics test tasks based on Bloom's taxonomy. According to it, when assessing students' knowledge in physics, we can form test tasks that are suitable for each student's knowledge, covering knowledge from the lowest cognitive level to the highest cognitive level, and evaluate each student's knowledge level objectively and transparently. On the basis of this taxonomy, S. Kambarova described in detail the stages of processing materials in her research. If we use taxonomy in the assimilation of information, it will help not only to correctly define the hunting goals, but also to implement them in harmony, in the correct orientation towards the result, intellectual skills and serves to develop abilities in a systematic way. G. Koysynova's research on

the correct and effective organization of students' free time is the most important link in the educational system. We can apply her research to every field and every branch of science.

It is appropriate to use Bloom's taxonomy in the organization of an educational environment in physics. Because physics is a science of natural existence, it studies the most common laws of nature, substances, their structure, the movement of bodies and the rules of their change. Physics is a natural science, but its laws and calculations are based on precision.

Bloom's taxonomy has several advantages:

1. It provides a simple structure for the learning process.
2. It is widely used in the field of business, especially in the field of training and development.
3. It can be applied to a very small learning process, such as child's learning process in kindergarten, school, academic high school and even higher education.

Based on Bloom's taxonomy, we need to follow the following in physics lessons:

- 1) To create learning objectives for the lesson and identify the taxonomy levels to be studied.
- 2) To provide adequate prior knowledge of the subject under consideration before starting a new study unit.
- 3) To engage students by using questions and activities at all levels of the taxonomy to encourage students to think critically about what they are learning, rather than simply recalling information as facts.
- 4) To provide opportunities for practical training or experiments so that students can see how the knowledge they have acquired can be applied to their own lives and environment. We can use this situation to organize laboratory classes on physics.
- 5) To provide feedback through assignments and discussions so students know where they stand at each level of understanding.

We have learned that using this taxonomy in physics lectures and practical lessons is effective. All researchers have given importance to these aspects. But if the student does not try the process he is studying in practice, he will not have a deep understanding of the essence of the subject, which areas it can be applied to. Therefore, in our research, we have given a number of suggestions and recommendations regarding the organization of laboratory work on physics based on Bloom's taxonomy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We can carry the application of Bloom's taxonomy from physics to laboratory activities as follows.

Theme: Determination of Planck's constant using the photo effect.

At the beginning of the lesson, the topic is introduced to the students, and the level of knowledge they have about this topic is checked, and questions about the level of knowledge of taxonomy are given.

Questions on knowledge level:

1. What does the word photo effect mean?
2. What is the phenomenon of photo effect?
3. What is the numerical value of Planck's constant?
4. Who was the first to thoroughly study the phenomenon of the photo effect?
5. How many types of photo effect are there?

The opinion of the students will be heard on the given questions and their level of knowledge of the subject will be determined. Then the following slide will be shown on the screen, which will further strengthen their knowledge. Pupils got a little understanding about the topic of the laboratory.

The next issue is to clarify the purpose of today's training. For this, the teacher creates a problem situation according to the level of understanding of Bloom's taxonomy.

Comprehension questions:

1. What is the significance of the photo effect phenomenon in the field of physics and what is the purpose of studying it?

2. How is Planck's constant related to this phenomenon?

In this situation, students will have an understanding of the importance of the photo effect phenomenon, why we need to study this phenomenon, and the importance of Planck's principle.

The purpose of the work: to study the phenomenon of photo effect and calculate Planck's constant through it.

After determining the purpose of the work, according to the level of application of the taxonomy, students determine Planck's constant from Einstein's equation for the photo effect. Papers in A4 format with the main formula written on them are distributed to students. In this process, they will have to determine the necessary formula for laboratory work.

FOTOEFFEKT HODISASI

$$h = \frac{e(U_2 - U_1)}{(v_2 - v_1)}$$

$$h\nu = A + \frac{mv^2}{2}$$

Ishni bajarish tartibi

1. "Nazariya" tugmasini bosib, Fotoeffekt hodisasi haqida ma'humot oling.
2. "Animatsiya" tugmasini bosib, yorug'lik ta'sirida katoddan elektronlar chiqishi hamda tok hosil bo'lib, Ampermetr va Voltmetr streklalarining o'g'ishini kuzating.
3. Tajribada fotoeffekt hodisasini bosib qiling.
4. Ikki hil yorug'lik chastotalari uchun Voltmetr ko'rsatishlarini yozib oling va jadvalga kiriting.
5. 3- va 4- punktlarni 3 marta takrorlang.
6. "Hisoblash" tugmasini bosing.
7. "Adabiyot" tugmasi orqali ko'rsatilgan adabiyotlardan qo'shimcha ma'lumotlar oling.
8. "Savollar" tugmasi orqali olgan bilimlaringizni sinab ko'ring.

U ₁	U ₂	v ₁	v ₂	h	Δh	σ
200	180	160	145	6.4	2506	4.165
200	211	176	168	7.2	5355	7.407
230	202	146	138	6.4	2506	4.165
216.59	204.33	153.33	158.33	5.659	3555	5.245

Hisoblash
Nazariya
Ish tartibi

Animatsiya
Savollar
Adabiyot

Bosh menyuga

After students complete the given task, they will be presented with a graphic organizer as follows. Because experience shows that graphic organizers have a special place in today's development period [5]. After determining the necessary formula for the calculation, the laboratory work is carried out. In each part of the work procedure, students are given concepts so that they understand what they are doing.

Questions to analyze:

1. What do the ammeter and voltmeter measure in the given diagram?
2. What type of photo effect phenomenon is observed in this process?
3. What quantities should we record during this experiment?

After analyzing each set of questions, students realize that they are working on a regular experiment. Work responsibility also increases. The students determine the required sizes and perform calculations.

The final conclusion part of the lab work remains, and the Synthesis and Evaluation parts of Bloom's Taxonomy are more appropriate for this process. At the level of Bloom's taxonomy called Synthesis, if we ensure that students fully analyze the laboratory work, summarize the ideas presented during the lesson, and make a conclusion and create a new idea in their mind, teacher's fulfillment of the task assigned to him during the lesson is considered excellently accomplished.

Problem 1.

Explain the similarities and differences between internal and external photo effects?

Problem 2.

Assume. You are a physicist and you are working on the phenomenon of the photo effect. What other factors would you pay attention to in this situation?

Problem 3.

Whether or not the frequency or wavelength of the incident light can cross the line. What condition is observed? Your opinion...

At the evaluation level, the students fully describe their conclusions regarding the laboratory work.

CONCLUSION. Therefore, the use of Bloom's taxonomy in the formation of laboratory exercises on physics ensures students' self-control and further increases their interest in science. Careful attention to each part of the lesson helps to develop the skills to express one's opinion independently and create something new.

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